

MULTIPLE GRID FOR COMPUTING THE COMPOSITE BEHAVIOR WITH SPECTRAL METHOD

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ABSTRACT

The local and overall nonlinear responses of composites are generally calculated by the Finite Element Method (FEM). This traditional FEM method requires meshing geometry and assembling stiffness matrix. Spectral method based on Fast Fourier Transforms directly using real microstructure images can avoid these steps. Composites with complex structure can be discretized into a set of regular grids. But grids cannot describe interface between fiber and matrix exactly. To circumvent this difficulty, we restructure the original pixels into three types: virgin matrix grid, virgin fiber grid and interface grid. The interface grid effective stiffness is determined approximately by using the laminate rules and homogenization technique. The results show that this approach can be used to estimate the effective material properties of many complex microstructures. Comparing with classical FFT-based method, multiple interface grids can improve the local solution quality and the accuracy of the predicted effective elastic properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is essential to study the mechanical responses of composite materials with complex microstructure. Usually, finite element method (FEM) [1-6] are used to study the nonlinear local and overall response of composite materials. However FEM should have mesh discretization and assemble stiffness matrix, which is really tedious, especially for complex structure. This conventional approach results in costly computations. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a quick and efficient method to solve the problem of the complex structure mechanics. Fast Fourier Transforms (FFT) introduced by Moulinec and Suquet [7-10] is powerful to study the mechanical responses of materials with complex structures, which may potentially improve the computation efficiency.

The major disadvantage of the FFT-based method is its poor convergence for composites with large jumps of material properties. To promote these methods, Eyre and Milton proposed an accelerated scheme, in which a modified integral equation was treated by means of the series expansion approach with grid refinement [12]. In addition, Michel [13] introduced an equivalent saddle-point formulation solving by the Augmented Lagrangian method, which can reduce the sensitivity to the mechanical contrast, even converges for infinite contrasts. Zeman [14] proposed conjugate gradient based solves to solve the problem in the linear case, then Lionel [15] extended this solver to a wide class of nonlinear behaviors.

Although there are many approaches to improve the FFT-based method, Gibbs' phenomenon can't be avoided, which is a local oscillation due to the truncated high order term of the Fourier series. Furthermore, the strong heterogeneity on the micro scale causes stress concentration at interface, so that a detailed understanding of the interface is vital to predict the material's macroscopic response.

In this paper, to circumvent this difficulty, we restructure the original pixels into three types: virgin matrix grid, virgin fiber grid and interface grid. This method can assign grids containing an interface with different stiffness from the constituent materials. These ideas are inspired by Kabel [16], where the discretization scheme involves a mixing rule for the effective stiffness of an interface grid.

2 NUMERICAL METHOD

2.1 The periodic Lippmann-Schwinger equation

The local strain field $\varepsilon(u(x))$ is split into an average E and a fluctuation term $\varepsilon(\mu^*(x))$

$$\varepsilon(u(x)) = E + \varepsilon(\mu^*(x)) \quad (1)$$

By assuming periodic boundary conditions, the fluctuating term μ^* is periodic. The unit cell image contains N pixels, and independent mechanical properties are assigned individually to each pixel. The elastic mechanics basic equations can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{div} \sigma(x) &= 0 & \forall x \in V \\ \sigma(x) &= c(x) : (\varepsilon(\mu^*(x)) + E) & \forall x \in V \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Because of the heterogeneity, this problem is equivalent to a homogeneous linear elastic body with stiffness c^0 subjected to a polarization field $\tau(x)$. As a result, the polarization field tensor can be defined as

$$\tau(x) = \delta c(x) : \varepsilon(\mu(x)), \quad \delta c(x) = c(x) - c^0 \quad (3)$$

By using the periodic, Green operator Γ^0 associated with c^0 , the solution of (2) can be expressed in real spaces with convolution, which can be written as

$$\varepsilon(\mu^*(x)) = -\Gamma^0 * \tau(x), \quad \forall x \in V \quad (4)$$

Considering the difficulty in computation, the Eq. (4) can be translated into Fourier spaces.

$$\hat{\varepsilon}(\xi) = -\hat{\Gamma}^0(\xi) : \hat{\tau}(\xi), \quad \forall \xi \neq 0, \hat{\varepsilon}(0) = 0 \quad (5)$$

When the reference material is isotropic, the periodic operator Γ^0 is explicitly expressed in Fourier space as follows.

$$\hat{\Gamma}^0(\xi) = \frac{1}{4 \mu^0 |\xi|^2} (\delta_{ki} \xi_h \xi_j + \delta_{hi} \xi_k \xi_j + \delta_{kj} \xi_h \xi_i + \delta_{hj} \xi_k \xi_i) - \frac{\lambda^0 + \mu^0}{\mu^0 (\lambda^0 + 2 \mu^0)} \frac{\xi_i \xi_j \xi_k \xi_h}{|\xi|^4} \quad (6)$$

where ξ_j denotes the discrete frequencies.

Thus, the problem reduces to the periodic Lippmann-Schwinger equation

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \varepsilon(u(x)) &= -\Gamma^0 * \tau(x) + E \\ \hat{\varepsilon}(\xi) &= -\hat{\Gamma}^0 : \hat{\tau}(\xi), \quad \forall \xi \neq 0, \quad \hat{\varepsilon}(0) = E \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

This governing equation can be solved by an integral algorithm.

2.2 Interface composite grids and laminate rules

The homogenization method based on fast Fourier transform (FFT) is computed on the pixels. In fact, such a grid could not solve accurately the problem of interface between fiber and matrix of different phase. Therefore, if a pixel grid has different components, the grid can be recognized as interface grid. Its stiffness is different from component materials. In this paper, we restructure the original pixels into three types: virgin matrix grid, virgin fiber grid and interface grid. The effective material properties of the interface grid can be determined properly.

2.2.1 Establish interface composite grids

The microstructure model containing single fiber and matrix was used to study the mechanical behavior. The geometry is described by an Office Visio format as shown in Figure 1(a), the blue and red areas denote fiber and matrix, respectively. Then, the original image can be discretized into N pixels. The unit cell is a square structure, for length is 10mm and the diameter of the fiber is 5mm. The material constants are $E_0 = 68.9e^9 Pa$, $E_1 = 400.0e^9 Pa$, $\nu_0 = 0.35$, $\nu_1 = 0.23$.

(a) Unit cell structure

(b) Structure of the new grid elements

Figure 1: The geometry of composites with complex microstructure

In order to consider the interface between fiber and matrix, some composite grids located interface are established. The original microscopic image pixels are redistricted as a big new grid. Red part as composite grids contains both constituents simultaneously as shown in Figure 1(b). It can be seen that the grey part of the unit cell contains only matrix, and the blue part of the unit cell contains only fiber.

2.2.2 Laminate interface stiffness

After reconstruction of pixels, the key step is assigning a material property to the interface grids. Kabel [16] assume that the interface between different phases is approximately linear with normal vector n . Inspired by the formula for a general laminate, the elastic tensor of the interface elements can be obtained by considering average volume mixing rule, which can be written as

$$\left(P + \lambda (C_w - \lambda Id)^{-1} \right)^{-1} = \left\langle \left(P + \lambda (C - \lambda Id)^{-1} \right)^{-1} \right\rangle \quad (8)$$

where, λ is chosen sufficiently large value, which should be larger than the largest eigenvalue of the stiffness matrices $C(x)$ for all x , and the four-tensor P can be expressed as

$$P_{ijkl} = \frac{1}{2} \left(n_i \delta_{jk} n_l + n_i \delta_{jl} n_k + n_j \delta_{ik} n_l + n_j \delta_{il} n_k \right) - n_i n_j n_k n_l \quad (9)$$

It is necessary to solve the equation for the unknown interface stiffness C_w . The projector P can be determined by substituting the value of normal vector and Kronecker δ into Eq. (9).

Normals are computed by connecting the center of mass of the dominant material with the center of the pixel. Then, the normalized normal can be computed as

$$\tilde{n} = \frac{1}{|S|} \int_s x dx - \frac{1}{|W|} \int_w x dx \quad n = \frac{\tilde{n}}{\|\tilde{n}\|} \quad (10)$$

where, W is a pixel, S is the union of the sub-pixels of the dominant phase. In order to calculate the related physical quantities, we need to get the discrete coordinates of the sub-pixels. The functions rely on the discrete coordinates which can be defined as

$$x_N^k = \frac{k_1 L_1}{N_1} e_1 + \frac{k_2 L_2}{N_2} e_2 \quad (11)$$

Analytic representations of the interfaces are available, and normal vectors in interface grids can be computed analytically.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The stress and strain of the composites in plane strain state can be obtained by using FFT-based method implemented efficiently with MATLAB. A prescribed uniform strain is defined by $E_{11} = 0.01$.

The trend of stress and strain distributions are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: stress ($\sigma_{11}, \sigma_{22}, \sigma_{12}$) and strain ($\epsilon_{11}, \epsilon_{22}, \epsilon_{12}$)

It can be found from the above figure that the stress and strain distribute regularly with periodic

characteristics. The maximum value of σ_{11} is 2 Gpa. It can be seen that local stress concentrations appear at the stepped block-like interface between the fiber and matrix. Figure 3(a) and (b) shows the loading direction stress component for two types of pixels, one without considering interface and the other considering interface.

Figure 3: Influence on the average stress σ_{11} .

In Figure 3(a), there is a local oscillation due to the Fourier-type discretization, particularly in the regions of the interface. Owing to using the technology of restructure, this phenomenon is significantly diminished as shown in Figure 3(b). The distribution of stress on the interface between fiber and matrix is more smooth. The maximum value of σ_{11} is 1.7 Gpa with considering composite pixels at interface, the treatment method at the interface really reduces the stress concentration phenomenon.

In order to further validate the accuracy of FFT-based method, we made a comparison of FFT-based homogenization method with experiment [17] by calculating average modulus as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: The change of the average modulus along with fiber volume fraction

From the example of two dimensional case, the predicted results of FFT-based method are accurate enough compared with the experiment results. With the increase of fiber volume fraction, the average modulus of the structure increased. An analysis of the above results show that the FFT-based method is a reasonable approach for computing the composite behaviors by using digital images directly, in which

the normal direction and properties of interface between fiber and matrix is taken into account.

The influence of the resolution is given in Figure 5. The resolution of the image is determined here through different number of pixels. Meanwhile, the fiber volume fraction is determined through fiber diameter d from 2mm to 8mm.

Figure 5. The effect of resolution on calculation efficiency and accuracy.

As shown in Figure 5(a), with the increase of the number of pixels, the number of iterations has a declining trend. As shown in Figure 5(b), the maximum value of σ_{11} is not very sensitive to resolution. However, the pink curve for 8mm fiber diameter shows that the higher resolution is required for the larger fiber volume fraction.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The proposed FFT based method is evaluated by using a single fiber embedded matrix geometry with regular grids, in which the normal direction and properties of interface between fiber and matrix is taken into account. The pixel restructure technique is an effective, simple and direct method to correct the spurious stresses introduced by the stepped block-liked interface at material junctions, which does not increase the computation costs during the calculation. Considering the interface in the composite grid as linear, the pixel located at interface is assigned the corresponding interface stiffness. This improvement can increase the local quality of the strain and stress fields dramatically.

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